

Influence of ICT Value in Teaching, Social Expectations on ICT, and Behavioral Control on Teachers' ICT Adoption

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ABSTRACT:

ICT adoption in teaching challenges educational institutions. This study determined the significance of ICT Value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control as predictors of ICT adoption in teaching. Utilizing multiple linear regression, 100 teachers were selected through purposive sampling, and it was found that only social expectations on ICT and behavioral control significantly predict the criterion variable. Though all the predictors account for 67.2 % of the degree of influence, the Theory of Planned Behavior was partially affirmed. Explore other variables to account for the 32.8 % variance in ICT adoption and prioritize teacher support to enhance ICT adoption and contribute to greater and equal access to quality education.

Keywords: ICT Value in teaching, Social Expectations on ICT, Behavioral Control, Teachers' ICT adoption.

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INTRODUCTION

ICT adoption in teaching continues to be a global challenge in both developed and developing nations [1]. Teachers have poor ICT adoption in the classroom [2]. In Malaysia, teachers faced difficulties in ICT adoption in classrooms with large student populations [3]. Meanwhile, in Liberia, ICT Adoption in education continues to be a struggle for teachers [4]. In Nigeria's Awka teachers had issues regarding ICT adoption in their instructional practice. [5]. In the Philippines, teachers faced a problematic situation practicing ICT adoption in teaching [6]. Tomaro [7] asserted that teachers have difficulties implementing ICT adoption inside the classroom. [8] also highlighted key issues in ICT adoption in the Philippines. Teachers' inability to adopt ICT hinders interactive teaching, limits access to diverse learning materials, and affects student performance, especially in developing essential digital skills [9]. [10] note that the rapid advancement of digital technologies and the increasing demand for 21st-century skills have made the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching not just beneficial but essential. In light of the strong demand for ICT adoption in teaching, there is limited empirical evidence on ICT adoption. These consequences push the urgency of this study. This urgency is coupled with the scarcity of research published concerning ICT adoption. It is in this context that this research is conducted.

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Statement of the Problem

The main purpose of this study is to determine the significance of ICT Value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control as predictors of teachers' ICT adoption in teaching.

Specifically, it achieved the following objectives:

1. To determine the levels of ICT value in teaching in terms of the usefulness of ICT and ease of Use of ICT; social expectations on ICT in terms of normative influence, institutional support, and professional recognition; behavioral control in terms of self-efficacy and controllability; and ICT adoption in teaching in terms of performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions among private junior high school teachers.
2. To determine the significance of the correlation between ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, behavioral control, and ICT adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers.
3. To determine the significance of the combined degree of influence of ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on ICT adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Ho1: ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control do not significantly correlate with ICT adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers.

Ho2: ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on ICT adoption do not significantly influence ICT Adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers.

Theory

This study is anchored on the Theory of Planned Behavior, developed by social psychologist [11], which is a behavioral theory that analyzes factors that affect behavioral intentions and, thus, explains behavior. According to the theory, the primary factor in predicting one's behavior is a shift in behavioral intentions [44]. It is dependent on attitude (either positive or negative), subjective norms (whether most people approve or disapprove of a behavior), and perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy [44].

In this study, the ICT Value in teaching indicated by the usefulness of ICT and ease of use of ICT [12] stands for the attitude towards the behavior in the theory. The social expectations on ICT indicated by normative influence, institutional support, and professional recognition [13] stand for the subjective norms as asserted in the theory. The behavioral control indicated by self-efficacy and controllability [14] stands for the perception of their control mentioned in the theory. Finally, ICT adoption in teaching is indicated by performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions [15].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized the quantitative research design with the descriptive-correlational method. According to [16], the descriptive method, also known as statistical research, describes data and characteristics of the population or phenomenon being studied. This method is used to collect data to test hypotheses or answer questions about the current state of the study's subject. This design facilitated the collection of quantifiable data, enabling an analysis of the relationships among the specified variables. The resulting insights are intended to guide educational practices and inform decision-making within private school contexts.

This study was conducted in selected private schools in Davao City, focusing on private junior high school teachers in the city. These schools were chosen to ensure a diverse educational experience and different levels of professional background. This diversity provided a comprehensive context for examining the influence of ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on ICT adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers.

The respondents of this study consisted of 100 private teachers selected through purposive sampling. According to [17], purposive sampling is a non-probability or non-random sampling technique chosen on the basis of the convenience of the investigator. The purposive sampling method was chosen to ensure that participants have a particular set of characteristics that make them suitable for the study. This approach ensured that data could be gathered effectively, capturing insights from teachers regarding the relationship between ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on the adoption of ICT in teaching.

[18] suggests that a sample size of 100 is generally acceptable for quantitative studies involving multivariate analysis, especially when examining moderate relationships between variables. [19] classify a sample size of 100 as "fair" and adequate for preliminary investigations or studies with straightforward designs and clearly defined variables.

The survey questionnaire was subjected to experts' validation and pilot testing. Validity was the extent to which an instrument measured what it was supposed to measure and performed as it was designed to perform [20,45]. The data from the pilot test were subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha as the index of reliability.

The researcher followed several steps to gather data for this study, including preparation, data collection, and analysis. First, the survey questionnaire guide was validated by experts. The manuscript was then revised based on recommendations from professors and panelists. It was subsequently submitted to SMILE (Society for Moral Integrity and Legal Ethics) for review.

An endorsement letter from the graduate school dean was requested to legitimize the study, accompanied by a formal request outlining its purpose and significance. Permission was also sought from relevant authorities, such as the school principal since the respondents were junior high school teachers from a private school. The survey questionnaire was administered online via Google Forms. Collected data were carefully tabulated and organized to ensure accuracy and readiness for interpretation. Throughout the process, the researcher prioritized the safety and well-being of all participants.

The researcher carried out the subsequent steps in analyzing the obtained data. Descriptive statistics, such as the weighted mean, were applied. The weighted mean was used to determine the levels of ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, behavioral control, and ICT adoption among junior high school teachers based on its indicators.

To establish the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, the researcher used Pearson's product-moment correlation [46]. Then, multiple linear regression was utilized to determine how ICT value, social expectations, and behavioral control influenced ICT adoption among junior high school teachers. Overall, the assumptions necessary for conducting multiple regression analysis were satisfactorily met. Despite minor concerns regarding normality, the data were deemed appropriate for further inferential analysis.

This study was conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines set forth by the DOST Philippine Health Research Board, the Code of Conduct by the American Psychological Association [21], and the Ethical Standards by the Psychological Association of the Philippines [22]. The researcher obtained informed consent from the teacher respondents, ensuring that their rights were respected. They were informed about the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, their right to withdraw at any point, and the measures taken to ensure their confidentiality.

To protect their identity, pseudonyms were used, and all data were anonymized and securely stored. No personally identifiable information was included in any reports or publications arising from the research. Participants were assured that their responses would remain confidential, and no real names or identifying details were disclosed. Additionally, the researcher strictly adhered to ethical protocols to avoid plagiarism, fabrication, falsification, and any conflict of interest. The principles and guidelines set forth by APA and PAP were followed throughout the research process.

RESULTS

Table 1 is a descriptive table. It contains the predictive variables involved in the study, namely ICT Value in teaching, Social Expectations on ICT, Behavioral Control on ICT adoption, and the criterion variable ICT adoption among private junior high school teachers. The number of samples, standard deviation, mean, and the corresponding descriptive level are also presented.

Table 1. Descriptive Table

Variables	n	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
ICT Value in teaching	100	0.42	4.68	Very High
Usefulness of ICT		0.36	4.78	Very High
Ease of Use of ICT		0.52	4.59	Very High
Social Expectations on ICT	100	0.63	4.31	Very High
Normative Influence		0.71	4.37	Very High
Institutional Support		0.57	4.50	Very High
Professional Recognition		1.02	4.05	High
Behavioral Control	100	0.42	4.68	Very High
Self-Efficacy		0.51	4.62	Very High
Controllability		0.49	4.53	Very High
ITC Adopting in Teaching	100	0.50	4.38	Very High
Performance Expectancy		0.47	4.49	Very High
Effort Expectancy		0.68	4.30	Very High
Socia Influence		0.61	4.45	Very High
Facilitating Conditions		0.69	4.29	Very High

As shown in Table 1, the ICT value in teaching among private junior high school teachers obtained an overall mean of 4.68, which is described as a very high level. This indicates that the ICT value in teaching is extremely strong. All its indicators obtained a corresponding mean very high level.

In addition, the social expectations on ICT among private junior high school teachers obtained an overall mean of 4.31, which is described as a very high level. It indicates that the social expectations on ICT are extremely strong. All its indicators obtained a corresponding mean of a very high level, except for professional recognition, which obtained a high level.

Furthermore, the behavioral control on ICT adoption among private junior high school teachers obtained an overall mean of 4.68, described as a very high level. It indicates that behavioral control on ICT adoption is extremely strong, as perceived by the respondents. All its indicators obtained a corresponding mean of a very high level.

Lastly, the ICT Adoption in teaching among private junior high school teachers obtained an overall mean of 4.38, described as a very high level. It indicates that ICT Adoption in teaching is excellent. All its indicators obtained a corresponding mean of a very high level.

Table 2 is a correlation table. It contains the predictive variables involved in the study, namely ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, behavioral control on ICT adoption, and the criterion variable ICT adoption in teaching. It also contains the r-value, p-value, the decision on the hypothesis, and the corresponding descriptive level.

Table 2. Correlation Table

Variables	ICT Adoption inTeaching			
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H_{01}	Interpretation
ICT Value in teaching	0.656	0.000	Reject	Significant
Social Expectations on ICT	0.774	0.000	Reject	Significant
Behavioral Control	0.735	0.000	Reject	Significant

The table specifically shows that the correlation between the ICT Value in teaching and ICT adoption in teaching obtained a p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 degree of confidence; hence, the

null hypothesis was rejected. It indicates that the correlation between the ICT Value in teaching and ICT adoption in teaching is significant. Furthermore, the correlation between the two variables obtained an r-value of 0.656, signifying a moderately high correlation.

On the other hand, the correlation between social expectations on ICT and ICT adoption in teaching obtained a p-value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 degree of confidence. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that the correlation of the two variables is significant. Furthermore, the obtained r-value of 0.774 signifies a high correlation.

Also, behavioral control on ICT adoption and ICT adoption in teaching obtained a p-value of .000, which is less than the 0.05 degree of confidence; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicates that the correlation of the two variables is significant. Furthermore, the obtained r-value of 0.735 signifies a high correlation.

Noticeably, since the three predictive variables obtained corresponding p-values which are less than 0.05 degree of confidence, they are significantly correlated with ICT adoption in teaching. This implies that for every unit change in the predictive variables, there is a corresponding positive unit change in the criterion variable.

Table 3 is a regression table. It contains the predictive variables involved in the study, namely ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, behavioral control on ICT adoption, and the criterion variable, which is the adoption of ICT in teaching. The table also contains the coefficient beta, standard error, t-value, p-value, decision on hypotheses, and the corresponding interpretations.

Table 3. Regression Table

Predictors	ICT Adoption in Teaching					
	Coefficients	Std. Est.	t	p	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Intercept	0.7404					
ICT Value in Teaching	0.0280	0.0234	0.235	0.815	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Social Expectations on ICT	0.3995	0.5021	5.810	0.000	Reject	Significant
Behavioral Control	0.3915	0.3645	3.609	0.000	Reject	Significant

Note: R=0.820, R²=0.672, Adjusted R²=0.662, Sig.=0.000

Table 3 specifically shows that ICT Value in teaching obtained a beta coefficient of 0.0280, signifying that it has a 2.80% degree of influence on ICT adoption. With the obtained p-value of 0.815, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected. It indicates that the 2.80% degree of ICT Value in teaching on ICT adoption is not significant.

Additionally, social expectations on ICT obtained a beta coefficient of 0.3995, signifying that it has a 39.95% degree of influence on ICT adoption in teaching. With the obtained p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. It indicates that a 39.95% degree of social expectations on ICT adoption in teaching is significant. This further implies that for every unit increase in social expectations on ICT, there is a corresponding 0.3995 unit increase in ICT adoption in teaching.

Also, behavioral control on ICT adoption obtained a beta coefficient of 0.3915, signifying that it has a 39.15% degree of influence on ICT adoption in teaching. With the obtained p-value of 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. It indicates that a 39.15% degree of behavior control on ICT adoption in teaching is significant. This further implies that for every unit increase in behavior control on ICT adoption, there is a corresponding 0.3915 unit increase in ICT adoption in teaching.

Overall, with the R²-value of **0.672**, it is indicated that the three predictive variables have a 67.2% combined degree of influence on ICT adoption in teaching. With the obtained p-value of 0.000, which is less than the 0.05 confidence level, it indicates that the combined degree of influence is significant.

Finally, the table shows the regression formula for ICT adoption in teaching, that is $ICTA = 0.0280 ICTV + 0.3995 SE + 0.3915 BC + 0.7404$.

Summary of Findings

1. ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on ICT adoption are extremely strong, and ICT adoption in teaching is excellent.
2. All the predictors significantly correlated with the criterion variable.
3. All the predictor variables significantly influence the criterion variable, except for the ICT value in teaching. Collectively, the predictors account for 67.2% combined degree of influence on the criterion variable.

DISCUSSION

ICT value in teaching is extremely strong. This finding about extremely strong ICT value in teaching among private JHS teachers affirms the studies of [23],[24] and [25] stating that the significant value of ICT in education, particularly in enhancing teaching and learning effectiveness, that ICT tools provide opportunities for students to develop 21st-century skills and engage in dynamic learning experiences, and ICT remains crucial in preparing students for successful careers in an increasingly technological world. However, it objects to the research that emphasizes that ICT should complement rather than replace traditional teaching methods, with teachers maintaining their crucial role in information delivery ([26].

Social Expectations on ICT is extremely strong. This finding about extremely strong social expectations on ICT among private JHS teachers confirms the studies of [27] and [28] that the development of ICTs has led to significant social changes, prompting a reevaluation of earlier predictions about their effects on society and democratic values, institutional support and professional development support ICT adoption.

However, it negates the studies of [29] and [30] that social expectations can sometimes have adverse effects, leading to resistance rather than adoption, and a study on tensions between technology integration practices and policy plans in Ghana found disparities between teachers' practices and ICT policy expectations, indicating that external pressures alone may not suffice to drive adoption without considering teachers' readiness and contextual factors.

Behavioral control on ICT adoption is extremely strong. This finding about extremely strong behavioral control on ICT adoption among private JHS teachers study affirms the studies of [31], [32], and [33] which emphasized that teachers with high self-efficacy and strong technological knowledge recognize ICT's usefulness and ease of use, reinforcing its perceived value, that teachers' confidence in ICT use is linked to their perceived control, aligning with the high self-efficacy and controllability ratings observed, and PBC significantly and positively influences users' intentions to adopt fintech services.

ICT Adoption in teaching is excellent. This finding about excellent ICT adoption in teaching among private JHS teachers corroborates with the studies by [34] and [35]. Said studies found that the adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in teaching has significantly enhanced educational practices and outcomes, and the adoption of ICT in education has been instrumental in transforming traditional teaching methods, enabling the incorporation of digital resources that cater to diverse learning needs. However, it contradicts a systematic review by [36], which identified persistent obstacles to ICT integration in higher education.

The findings reveal a significant correlation between ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on the adoption of ICT, and the ICT adoption in teaching among private JHS teachers, asserts the studies of [37], [38], and [39]. These studies indicate that when teachers recognize the value of ICT in enhancing teaching and learning, they are more inclined to adopt it and that social expectations and institutional support are pivotal in encouraging teachers to integrate ICT into their teaching methodologies. Moreover, it is indicated that when teachers perceive adequate

support and resources (facilitating conditions), they feel more in control and confident in adopting ICT.

The findings reveal that ICT value in teaching, social expectations on ICT, and behavioral control on ICT adoption significantly influence ICT adoption in teaching. It affirms the studies of [40] and [41] that showed subjective norms, attitudes towards technology, and perceived behavioral control positively affected the behavioral intention to use ICT in HEIs among academicians [47] and that the subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and social expectations also play significant roles in ICT adoption.

However, it disagrees with the study of [42] that, in certain contexts, social expectations might not be a strong predictor of ICT adoption. The finding also contradicts the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) model identifies performance expectancy (akin to perceived usefulness) as a direct predictor of behavioral intention to use technology by [43].

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that social expectations on ICT and behavioral control on ICT adoption are significant determinants of ICT adoption in teaching. The ICT value in teaching was found as not a significant predictor. Despite the 67.2% combined degree of influence on the criterion's variable, the Theory of Planned Behavior was partially affirmed, stating that the primary factor in predicting one's behavior is a shift in behavioral intentions and is dependent on attitude [44], subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion, it is recommended that future research utilizing other variables not covered in this study may be undertaken to account for the remaining 32.8 % variance in ICT adoption in teaching. Furthermore, social expectation and Behavioral control among teachers may be prioritized in the educational setting towards a greater benefit in ICT adoption. These interests ultimately contribute to the attainment of equal access to quality education (SDG 4).

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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